

APPLICATION OF MIXTURE LAW TO RHEOCHOR

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The rheochor values obtained by mixture law fall with the increase in temperature in case of acetic acid, urea and acetamide and show a closer approximation to the calculated values at higher temperatures. Monochloroacetic acid behaves differently.

Bhagwat and Tosniwal (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 30) have advanced the view that solution method may be applicable to rheochor also and hence suggested that like parachor, rheochor can be determined by the solution method both for liquids and solids by the expression,

$$R_m = R(1-x) + x.R_x$$

where R_m is the rheochor of the solution, R , the rheochor of the solvent, R_x , the rheochor of the solute and x , the molecular fraction of the solute. R_m is given by the expression

$$R_m = \frac{M_m \eta^1}{D}$$

where M_m is the mean molecular weight of the solution, η , the viscosity of the solution, D , the density of the solution. M_m is obtained from the equation,

$$M_m = M(1-x) + M_x,$$

where M is the molecular weight of the solvent and M_x is the molecular weight of the solute.

We have determined the viscosities at room temperature and at the boiling point of water. The viscosity at the room temperature was determined as usual.

To determine the viscosity at the boiling point of water the viscometer is fitted up by means of a cork into a conical flask of about one litre capacity. Through the cork passes a tube bent at right angles to let the steam out. The viscometer is thoroughly cleaned, dried and filled with a known volume of the liquid (whose viscosity is required). By means of the rubber tubing liquid is sucked in the narrower tube of the viscometer till the level of liquid is a little above the upper mark, and the rubber tubing closed by means of a pinch-cock. This is done to avoid the formation of air-bubbles, which invariably takes place if the sucking is done when the water is boiling, and causes an obstruction in the downward flow of the liquid, resulting in the fluctuation of the value of time of fall for the liquid through the capillary. The flask is filled with enough water to cover the upper mark, and heated, some porous pieces being put in the flask to cause regular boiling. When the water has been boiling for about 15 minutes, so that the liquid in the viscometer attains the temperature of boiling water, the time of fall for the liquid between two fixed marks is noted by a stopwatch. The temperature of the liquid is also noted.

The viscometer is cleaned, dried, and after filling with an equal volume of water, the time of fall for the water is determined exactly as in the case of the liquid.

The viscosity is calculated by the usual expression and rheochor is calculated by Newton Friend's formula. Results obtained are given below

TABLE I

Rheochor of water at different temperatures

Temp.	Density.	Viscosity.	Rheochor.	Temp.	Density.	Viscosity.	Rheochor.
20°	0.9982	10.05	24.19	25°	0.9979	8.937	23.59
20.6	0.9981	9.926	24.03	30	0.9957	8.007	23.45
21.6	0.9979	9.694	23.96	40	0.9926	6.560	22.94
22	0.9978	9.605	23.94	50	0.9881	5.490	22.59
22.5	0.9977	9.638	23.92	97	0.9605	2.936	21.13

The values of density and viscosity shown in the above table are taken from standard tables.

TABLE II

Rheochor of methyl alcohol in water

Rheochor (calc.) = 49.3. Temp. = 25°.

x	M_m .	D .	η .	R_m .	R_x .
0.3578	24.06	0.9221	14.25	36.24	58.89
0.2948	22.14	0.9313	14.26	33.16	56.08
0.2681	21.75	0.9387	14.61	32.47	56.69
0.1282	19.79	0.9679	12.47	28.05	58.34

The values at room temperature are high. Due to rapid evaporation of methyl alcohol at the boiling point of water, results could not be obtained.

TABLE III

Rheochor of acetic acid in water

Rheochor (calc.) = 74. Temp. = 25°

x .	M_m .	D .	η .	R_m .	R_x .
0.1617	25.06	1.049	15.72	33.70	84.14
0.1338	23.62	1.040	11.92	31.00	80.41
0.1141	22.70	1.038	13.52	30.40	83.35
0.0780	21.17	1.028	12.02	28.21	82.81
0.0638	20.68	1.026	11.51	27.36	82.60
1.0000	60.00	1.047	9.605	..	76.03

The results are higher but they approach theoretical value at the boiling point of water.

TABLE IV

Rheochor of acetic acid in water at different temperatures

19.789 g. of acetic acid dissolved in 34.4386 g. of water. $x=0.1338$, $(1-x)=0.8662$, $M_m=23.62$.

Temp.	D .	η .	R_m .	R_x .
30°	1.040	13.33	31.39	82.21
40	1.036	10.57	30.63	80.41
50	1.032	8.332	29.84	76.83

TABLE V

Rheochor of acetic acid in water at boiling point (97°).

x .	M_m .	D .	η .	R_m .	R_x .
1.0000	60.0	1.003	4.527	.	72.24
0.3748	33.74	1.037	5.573	40.32	72.35
0.1795	25.53	1.028	4.684	30.12	71.19
0.06703	21.00	1.020	3.681	24.24	69.00

TABLE VI

Rheochor of acetamide in water at 22.5°

Rheochor (calc.) = 72.7

x .	M_m .	D .	η .	R_m .	R_x .
0.07575	21.10	1.015	14.70	29.09	91.62
0.07191	20.94	1.013	17.16	29.49	100.6
0.04290	19.76	1.009	12.62	26.89	92.3
0.03629	19.49	1.007	11.49	26.27	89.28
0.03616	19.48	1.007	11.55	26.69	100.7
0.02282	18.94	1.006	12.22	25.76	102.1

The results as accepted are higher at room temperature ; but they fall at the boiling point.

TABLE VII

Rheochor of acetamide in water at 97°.

x .	M_m .	D .	η .	R_m .	R_x .
0.07291	21.00	1.012	3.946	24.63	69.11
0.0702	20.99	1.012	3.752	24.62	70.94
0.0429	19.76	1.006	3.650	23.10	57.27
0.03629	19.49	1.003	3.303	22.51	59.24
0.0303	19.36	1.001	3.342	22.47	61.76
0.0329	19.35	0.999	3.350	22.53	63.83
0.03204	19.37	1.001	3.877	22.95	84.64
0.03099	19.17	1.004	3.387	22.29	60.66
0.02832	19.16	1.006	3.402	22.20	58.96

TABLE VIII

Rheochor of urea in water at room temperature (21.6°).

Rheochor (calc.) = 64.00.

x .	M_m .	D .	η .	R_m .	R .
0.07068	20.02	1.053	12.23	27.04	67.48
0.0565	20.43	1.049	11.57	26.44	68.01
0.05343	20.20	1.045	11.01	26.09	64.04
0.04201	19.78	1.036	10.72	25.68	65.00
0.0219	18.92	1.021	9.356	24.62	54.34

The results fairly agree at room temperature but fall as the temperature is increased.

TABLE IX

Rheochor of urea in water at 96°

x .	M_m .	D .	η .	R_m .	R_x .
0.07845	21.29	1.054	3.928	23.95	57.11
0.06916	20.90	1.048	3.873	23.61	58.97
0.06560	20.76	1.048	3.872	23.36	55.24
0.06548	20.75	1.047	3.803	23.42	56.19
0.04586	19.92	1.031	3.525	22.61	53.42

Rheochor of monochloroacetic acid in water at 20.2°.

Rheochor (calc.) = 97.1.

x_1	M_m	D	η	R_m	R_x
0.05294	22.07	1.086	15.10	28.52	92.55
0.03355	20.56	1.066	12.54	26.71	99.56
0.02510	19.92	1.045	11.58	25.89	102.0
0.02477	19.90	1.041	11.95	26.07	106.1
0.02204	19.69	1.042	12.08	25.80	98.95
0.01308	19.00	1.025	11.07	25.03	98.65

Rheochor of monochloroacetic acid in water at 96°.

0.04348	22.13	1.062	3.517	24.33	115.2
0.0356	21.43	1.067	3.975	23.86	111.6
0.0240	19.84	1.040	3.567	22.37	110.4
0.01816	19.39	1.032	3.534	22.00	119.0

Monochloro-acetic acid shows a peculiar behaviour, that its rheochor values increase with temperature.

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